

Multiple Bilateral Fibroadenomas Associated with A Benign Phyllodes Tumor in a Young Patient: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Fibroadenomas are the most common benign tumors of the breast; however, their presentation as multiple and bilateral lesions is uncommon, particularly in young patients. Coexistence with a benign phyllodes tumor is exceptional and poses diagnostic and therapeutic challenges.

Case presentation: We report the case of an 18-year-old woman with intellectual disability who presented with multiple painful bilateral breast masses of eight months' duration. Physical examination revealed approximately ten bilateral breast nodules. Breast ultrasonography demonstrated multiple oval lesions with circumscribed margins, classified as BI-RADS 3. Due to the multiplicity, size of the lesions, and associated symptoms, surgical management was chosen without prior biopsy. Complete resection of the lesions was performed through a single circumferential periareolar incision using the round-block technique. Histopathological examination revealed multiple bilateral pericanalicular fibroadenomas and three benign phyllodes tumors with negative surgical margins. Postoperative evolution was favorable, with complete resolution of pain and no complications. Clinical and imaging follow-up at 3 and 6 months showed no recurrence.

Conclusion: This case illustrates an uncommon presentation of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas associated with benign phyllodes tumors in a young patient. Conservative surgical management using the round-block technique allowed adequate resection with favorable clinical and aesthetic outcomes. The importance of an individualized diagnostic approach and close follow-up in rare presentations of fibroepithelial breast tumors is emphasized.

KEYWORDS: Breast fibroadenoma, benign phyllodes tumor, fibroepithelial tumors, multiple breast lesions, round-block technique, bilateral breast, adolescent, breast-conserving surgery.

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INTRODUCTION

Fibroadenomas are benign tumors composed of epithelial and fibrous tissue and represent the most common breast lesions or masses in women. They occur predominantly in women of reproductive age, particularly those younger than 30 years. They typically present as slow-growing lesions, usually measuring up to 3 cm, and in most cases appear as solitary

masses. However, multiple breast fibroadenomas are uncommon, occurring in approximately 15%–20% of women. Affected patients may experience psychological distress due to the evident irregularity of the breasts.¹

Most fibroadenomas do not recur after complete excision; however, in adolescent patients, one or more new fibroadenomas may develop in areas adjacent to the previous

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surgical site in the same breast or even in the contralateral breast. The average number of masses reported in cases of multiple fibroadenomas is three to four in a single breast, while the presence of more than five fibroadenomas in the same patient is considerably less frequent. Unlike women with solitary fibroadenomas, most patients with multiple fibroadenomas have a positive family history of these tumors.^{1,2} The exact etiology of multiple breast fibroadenomas has not been clearly defined. A possible association with the use of hormonal or oral contraceptives has been proposed, although this relationship has not been conclusively documented in the literature. Other proposed pathogenic mechanisms include in vivo estrogen imbalance, hypersensitivity of breast tissue to estrogens, dietary factors, or hereditary predisposition. Another hypothesis suggests that even when estrogen levels remain within physiological ranges, an increased number of estrogen receptors may result in heightened tissue sensitivity, potentially leading to breast gland hyperplasia and even carcinoma development.^{2,3}

The pathogenesis underlying the formation of numerous breast fibroadenomas in a single patient remains unknown. It has been postulated that constant estrogenic stimulation of breast tissue and/or increased estrogen sensitivity during adolescence may promote a marked increase in both the size and number of fibroadenomas. Some authors define giant fibroadenomas as those larger than 5 cm; however, this definition is not universally accepted.^{2,4}

Although fibroadenomas are common in the general population, they rarely present in a multiple and bilateral form. Among women with fibroadenomas, only a minority present with two to four masses in a single breast, and an even smaller proportion have bilateral involvement. In the adolescent population, fibroadenomas are relatively uncommon. Published data on women with multiple bilateral fibroadenomas are limited and mainly restricted to case reports, many of which lack detailed genetic information.^{3,4} The present article reports an uncommon presentation of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas associated with a benign phyllodes tumor in a young patient, as well as its diagnostic approach, surgical management, and clinical outcome.

CASE REPORT

An 18-year-old nulliparous woman of mestizo ethnicity with a history of intellectual disability presented for evaluation due to multiple bilateral breast lumps associated with progressively worsening breast pain over approximately eight months. The pain constituted the main reason for consultation and the predominant complaint reported by her caregivers.

Gynecologic history revealed menarche at 13 years of age with regular menstrual cycles. She denied current or prior use of hormonal contraceptives. No family history of breast disease,

neoplasms, or other relevant hereditary conditions was documented, nor was there a history of exposure to ionizing radiation. Genetic evaluation was not performed. From a psychosocial standpoint, the patient lived with her family, did not smoke, consume alcohol, or use illicit substances, did not engage in physical activity, and did not take regular medications. She attended a special education school for individuals with intellectual disability.

As a relevant medical history, the patient's intellectual disability significantly limited verbal communication. During painful episodes, discomfort was expressed through crying and pointing to the breast region, without the ability to verbally quantify pain. She had no other comorbidities or prior surgical history.

On general physical examination, the patient weighed 80 kg and measured 164 cm in height, with a body mass index of 29.7 kg/m², consistent with overweight. Breast inspection showed preserved symmetry, with no skin changes, nipple-areola complex retraction, or pathological discharge. Palpation revealed approximately ten bilateral nodular masses, firm, well-circumscribed, mobile, not fixed to deep planes, some painful on palpation, distributed across different breast quadrants and radial positions. Clinically estimated sizes ranged from approximately 1 to 8 cm, with several large-volume lesions. No clinically pathological axillary lymphadenopathy was identified.

Bilateral breast ultrasonography was performed using a high-frequency linear transducer (12–4 MHz). The skin and subcutaneous tissue were unremarkable, with homogeneous fibroglandular echotexture. Multiple bilateral oval nodules with circumscribed margins and parallel orientation were identified and classified as BI-RADS 3. In the right breast, lesions were observed in the interline of the outer quadrants measuring 84 × 38 × 77 mm; in the interline of the inner quadrants measuring 60 × 24 × 40 mm; at the 11:00 position, 5 cm from the nipple, measuring 26 × 34 × 18 mm; at the 5:00 position, 5 cm from the nipple, measuring 32 × 25 × 37 mm; at the 2:00 position, 5 cm from the nipple, measuring 5 × 12 × 7 mm; and at the 3:00 position, 5 cm from the nipple, measuring 16 × 8 × 15 mm.

In the left breast, lesions were identified at the 12:00 position, 3 cm from the nipple, measuring 44 × 38 × 29 mm; at the 4:00 position, 2 cm from the nipple, measuring 38 × 33 × 23 mm; at the 7:00 position, 2 cm from the nipple, measuring 25 × 19 × 12 mm; and at the 11:00 position, 3 cm from the nipple, measuring 41 × 27 × 38 mm. Several lesions were predominantly hypoechoic and heterogeneous, with mixed posterior acoustic enhancement and minimal peripheral vascularity on color Doppler. Additionally, multiple anechoic nodules smaller than 5 mm with posterior acoustic enhancement were observed. Retroareolar regions showed no ductal ectasia. In both axillae, lymph nodes with preserved morphology, fatty hilum, and

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normal cortical thickness were identified; accessory breast tissue was noted in the right axilla. Ultrasound measurements were expressed in millimeters.

Given the multiplicity, size of the lesions, and associated symptoms, surgical management without prior biopsy was chosen. This decision was based on clinical presentation, imaging findings, and therapeutic necessity. Diagnostic considerations included multiple fibroadenomas as the primary diagnosis, with phyllodes tumor, diffuse fibroadenomatosis, and pseudoangiomatous stromal hyperplasia as differential diagnoses.

Surgical resection was performed through a single circumferential periareolar incision using the round-block technique, allowing removal of all breast lesions (Figure 1). Intraoperative blood loss was approximately 80 mL. A surgical drain was placed and removed the following day due to minimal output. Surgical specimens were sent separately and labeled according to anatomical location, correlating lesion size and radial position with ultrasonographic findings.

Histopathological examination revealed multiple bilateral pericanalicular fibroadenomas, some with sclerotic changes, without atypia, measuring between 0.9 cm and 8.4 cm in greatest dimension (Figure 2). In the left breast, three lesions consistent with benign phyllodes tumors were identified, one of

which contained microcalcifications. These tumors were characterized by a leaf-like pattern, mild stromal cellularity, and absence of stromal overgrowth, necrosis, or significant mitotic activity. Surgical margins were negative. Histopathological measurements were expressed in centimeters (Figure 3).

Perioperative management included preoperative antimicrobial prophylaxis with intravenous cefazolin 1 g prior to surgery. Postoperatively, analgesia with paracetamol 500 mg every 8 hours and ketorolac 10 mg every 8 hours was prescribed, both well tolerated without the need for dose adjustment or discontinuation. No adverse events related to the procedure or medications were observed. Due to the elevated body mass index, the patient was referred to the nutrition service for comprehensive management of overweight with a preventive approach.

Postoperative evolution was favorable. No complications such as fever, seroma, hematoma, wound dehiscence, infection, persistent pain, or hypertrophic scarring occurred. Clinically, complete resolution of breast pain was documented. According to caregivers, the patient no longer exhibited episodes of crying or pointing to the breast region. Follow-up at 3 and 6 months postoperatively with physical examination and breast ultrasonography showed no evidence of recurrence.

Figure 1: Postoperative image of the breast showing a circumferential periareolar incision (round-block technique), with proper edge approximation and no signs of infection or wound dehiscence..

Figure 2: Photomicrograph at 40x magnification showing a biphasic breast lesion composed of ductal elements without atypia and stromal elements within a hypocellular myxoid background, consistent with fibroadenoma.

Figure 3: Photomicrograph at 10× magnification showing areas with large fronds composed of ductal elements without atypia, with increased stromal cellularity and mild stromal atypia, without heterologous elements, consistent with a benign phyllodes tumor.

DISCUSSION

The discussion of the present case addresses the clinical, diagnostic, and therapeutic aspects of a rare presentation of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas associated with a benign phyllodes tumor, comparing our findings with existing reports and highlighting their implications for clinical management.

Im et al. described a case report of a young woman with early-onset multiple bilateral fibroadenomas in whom a pathogenic germline mutation in the PTEN gene was identified after genetic testing prompted by the unusual presentation, despite the patient not initially meeting established clinical criteria for evaluation. This case emphasized the association between early-onset multiple bilateral fibroadenomas, Cowden syndrome, and an increased risk of breast cancer.⁴ In contrast, although our patient presented an equally unusual manifestation due to lesion multiplicity, bilaterality, and young age, no suggestive family history was documented, genetic evaluation was not performed, and histopathological findings corresponded to multiple fibroadenomas and benign phyllodes tumors, with favorable clinical evolution and no evidence of recurrence during follow-up.

Eni et al. reported a case of multiple bilateral breast fibroadenomas in a 20-year-old woman with painful masses of eight months' duration. Diagnosis was established through clinical examination, imaging studies, and cytology, and treatment consisted of surgical resection of eleven lesions via a Gaillard-Thomas incision, with favorable postoperative outcomes and histopathological confirmation.¹ This report is comparable to ours regarding early age of presentation, bilaterality and multiplicity of lesions, and surgical management as the treatment of choice.

Nikumbh et al. described an exceptional case of bilateral giant juvenile fibroadenomas in a prepubertal patient, highlighting its rarity and successful management with conservative surgery.

Although our patient did not present giant juvenile fibroadenomas, both cases share bilaterality, lesion multiplicity, and the usefulness of a conservative surgical approach with favorable outcomes.⁵ Santiago-Sanabria et al. reported a case of bilateral phyllodes tumor in an adult woman treated surgically with free margins and no recurrence.⁶ In comparison, although our patient was significantly younger and presented multiple bilateral fibroadenomas associated with a benign phyllodes tumor, both cases underscore the rarity of bilateral involvement and the importance of adequate surgical management and follow-up.

Collectively, cases described in the literature confirm that the presentation of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas is uncommon and exhibits wide variability in patient age, number of lesions, and therapeutic approach. Our case adds to this spectrum of unusual presentations and is distinguished by the coexistence of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas and a benign phyllodes tumor in a young patient—an exceptionally rare combination—highlighting the need for individualized diagnostic evaluation and appropriate surgical management with close follow-up.

From a surgical standpoint, the round-block technique has been described as an effective alternative for the treatment of multiple and multicentric benign breast lesions, as it allows access to different quadrants through a single periareolar incision, resulting in minimal scarring and favorable aesthetic outcomes. Several studies have demonstrated that this technique can be safely applied regardless of breast size, areolar diameter, or lesion location, making it a particularly advantageous option in young patients.^{7,8} This technique was used in our patient with favorable results and no complications. Regarding diagnostic reasoning, although the lesions were classified as BI-RADS 3 on imaging studies, their multiplicity, bilaterality, size, and associated symptoms justified the decision to proceed with surgical management for both diagnostic and

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therapeutic purposes. Differential diagnoses considered included multiple fibroadenomas, phyllodes tumor, diffuse fibroadenomatosis, and pseudoangiomatous stromal hyperplasia, with surgical excision being essential to establish the definitive histopathological diagnosis.

The coexistence of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas and a benign phyllodes tumor observed in our patient represents a clinically relevant finding within the spectrum of fibroepithelial breast tumors. Accurate histopathological differentiation is essential due to its therapeutic and prognostic implications. In this case, the achievement of negative surgical margins allowed for conservative management with clinical and imaging surveillance. Follow-up at 3 and 6 months showed no evidence of recurrence, supporting the effectiveness of surgical treatment, although the need for long-term surveillance is acknowledged.

Finally, this case highlights the importance of considering the functional and psychosocial impact of multiple breast lesions, particularly in patients with intellectual disability, in whom assessment of pain and quality of life may be limited. Resolution of pain and disappearance of crying episodes following surgery constituted clinically relevant outcomes. Key strengths of this case include detailed documentation of an uncommon presentation, adequate clinical, imaging, and histopathological correlation, and the use of a conservative surgical approach via the round-block technique, allowing complete resection of multiple lesions with favorable functional and aesthetic results. Complete pain resolution and objective clinical improvement further reinforce the benefit of surgical management. Limitations of this report include its single-case nature, lack of genetic evaluation, and relatively short follow-up period; nevertheless, it provides valuable information by documenting a rare presentation and a successful surgical approach.

From the caregivers' perspective, the patient experienced clear clinical improvement after surgical intervention, reflected in the resolution of breast pain and crying episodes, representing a positive impact on her well-being and daily quality of life.

CONCLUSION

The presentation of multiple bilateral fibroadenomas associated with a benign phyllodes tumor is exceptional, particularly in young patients. This case demonstrates that an individualized diagnostic approach and conservative surgical management using the round-block technique can achieve adequate resection, symptom resolution, favorable aesthetic outcomes, and absence of recurrence during early follow-up. These findings underscore the importance of clinical and imaging surveillance and provide relevant information for the management of similar rare presentations.

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Conflict of Interest: None.

Ethical Considerations: The patient and her family were fully informed at all times about the diagnosis, procedures performed, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for surgical and anesthetic procedures and for publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and institutional hospital regulations.

REFERENCIAS

- I. Eni, U. E., Isikhuemen, M. E., Eliboh, M. O., Sunday-Adeoye, I., Ekwedigwe, K. C., & Lengmang, S. (2017). *Case report of multiple breast fibroadenomas in a young Nigerian woman*. *Revista Brasileira de Mastologia*, 27(1), 16–19
<https://doi.org/10.5327/Z201700010016RBM>
- II. Zhang, R. R., Bevan, S., Sun, P., Lu, J. Z., & Peng, Y. (2012). *Unusual presentation of multiple fibroadenomas in bilateral breasts and accessory axillary breast*. *Breast Cancer: Basic and Clinical Research*, 6, 95–99.
<https://doi.org/10.4137/BCBCR.S9512>
- III. Conde, D. M., Morais, L. C., Pacheco, C. F., Ferreira, R. B., Sousa-e-Silva, É. P., Fonseca, P. S. P., & Pinto, S. A. (2017). *Multiple bilateral breast fibroadenomas and accessory axillary breast: A case report*. *Revista Brasileira de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia*, 39(2), 75–79.
- IV. Im, C. J., Miller, A., Balassanian, R., & Mukhtar, R. A. (2021). *Early-onset, multiple, bilateral breast fibroadenomas: A case report*. *BMC Women's Health*, 21(1), Article 170.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-021-01311-7>
- V. Nikumbh, D. B., Desai, S. R., Madan, P. S., Patil, N. J., & Wader, J. V. (2011). *Bilateral giant juvenile fibroadenomas of the breast: A case report*. *Pathology Research International*, 2011, Article 482046.
<https://doi.org/10.4061/2011/482046>
- VI. Santiago-Sanabria, L., López-Valle, M. Á., Garza-Arrieta, J., et al. (2022). *Bilateral phyllodes tumor: A rare form of clinical presentation. Case report*. *Ginecología y Obstetrícia de México*, 90(11), 933–941.
- VII. Panda, S. K., Patro, B., Mishra, J., Dora, R. K., & Subudhi, B. S. K. (2014). *Multiple fibroadenomas in bilateral breasts in a 46-year-old Indian woman: A case report*. *International Journal of Surgery Case Reports*, 5(5), 262–264.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2013.12.013>

VIII. Lovasić, F., Petković, M., Belac-Lovasić, I., Mustać, E., Uravić, M., & Zelić, M. (2011). *The “round-*

block” surgical technique in the management of multicentric fibroadenomas. Collegium Antropologicum, 35(1), 235–240